

Project Ideas from the Reactor Physics with Python Course

Zsolt Elter^{1,*}

¹Uppsala University, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Division of Applied Nuclear Physics, Sweden

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804110

ABSTRACT

The Reactor Physics with Python course is offered at Uppsala University since 2021. The course is built on active learning, offering datalabs to support the teaching material, and including programming based home assignments. The last task the students have to perform is a project assignment, where the students perform a research-like task, involving scientific computing and data analysis extending the content of the course. The projects can be selected from a number proposed exercises, or the students can bring their own proposed task. The course is currently offered as a self-paced, distance course.

This paper intends to review the selectable programming exercises, to share ideas with teachers of similar courses.

Keywords: reactor physics, neutronics, education, open sourced, python

1. INTRODUCTION

Uppsala university offers a bachelor's level, 1-year programme in nuclear engineering, which includes an introductory reactor physics course, intended for engineers students. However, due to the lack of a master's level nuclear engineering programme, there is no in-depth reactor physics course available for physics and engineering physics students. To fill this gap, it was decided in 2021 to introduce a new course, Reactor Physics with Python (RFP, which stands for *Reaktorfysik med Python*) as a selectable course [1]. The course is offered for 5 ECTS credits, which is equivalent to 133 working hours of work. Over the years, with 15-25 students from various Swedish universities finishing the course annually, the course grew into one of the largest and most popular reactor physics courses in Sweden.

The course is offered as a distance, self-paced summer course with asynchronous teacher supervision. Only limited and optional synchronous sessions are organized. In such a setting, active learning is more efficient, therefore the course is heavily built around interactive exercises, where students need to actively engage with the course material using the scientific computing toolbox.

Student examination in a distance course can be cumbersome, therefore besides a set of home assignments, project assignments were adopted as the final examination in the course. Initially, the projects focused on literature review and essay writing related to more advanced reactor physics topics, not covered by the course itself. However, students noted early on that programming exercises would be more appreciated as it is more in line with the spirit of the course. Therefore, over the last years several project topics were proposed, which are not trivial, but can be solved within 8-10 hours of work. It must be also noted that in view of the recent development in generative AI assistants, moving away from essay writing exercises was a fortunate decision.

An other notable feature of the RFP course is that the whole course material is open sourced and freely available [2]. As part of sharing the course material, this paper intends to introduce some of the offered project tasks, to provide inspiration to teachers of similar courses. Section 2 reviews the curriculum and structure of the course and Section 3 reviews a selected number of project tasks.

*zsolt.elter@physics.uu.se

2. SYLLABUS AND STRUCTURE

The aim of the course is to prepare students, both from a physics and a programming perspective, to be able to complete more advanced courses dealing with computational methods in reactor physics in the future. However it is acknowledged that not all student want to become methods developer, therefore the course prepares students also to be eligible for neutronic, safety or criticality analyst positions or just to provide a generic introduction to reactor physics. The course is designed for MSc student, however we typically have BSc students as well, furthermore we offer the course to PhD students in applied nuclear physics who have no prior background in reactor physics.

The nine lectures of the course cover the typical topics of introductory reactor physics classes: nuclear physics fundamentals (radioactive decay, nuclear reactions, cross sections, fission), neutron moderation and spectrum, neutron transport and diffusion, point kinetics, measurements in subcritical systems (1/M, Sjöstrand method, Rossi-alpha), and depletion. Based on the author's experience as a student, it can be confusing for learners if the actual physical treatment and the approximate solution methods of the equations are mixed within an introductory course (for example, the neutron transport equation versus the PN approximation). Therefore, this course only briefly mentions deterministic reactor physics calculation methods and includes a separate exercise session that covers the numerical solution of the diffusion equation. At the same time, the core material includes a short introduction to Monte Carlo particle transport methods, since our experience shows that these are much more effective in promoting an intuitive understanding of neutron transport.

The recommended reading for this course is, "Nuclear Reactor Analysis" by Duderstadt and Hamilton. In addition, the course material has been summarized in freely accessible lecture notes. What makes these lecture notes special is that the scientific figures were not borrowed from other books, but were generated using Python. By making the corresponding source code available, students have the opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of what each figure represents.

The course also includes 11 computer-based laboratory exercises, each consisting of one or, in some cases, two Jupyter Notebooks. The Notebooks are designed so that students can complete the exercises independently, without instructor assistance, as all necessary instructions are included within them. The first three exercises serve as an introduction to the Python programming language and the libraries used later in the course, while the remaining exercises focus on reactor physics itself. Each laboratory session contains multiple tasks, which we refer to as "experiments" to emphasize that students are free to modify various parameters and explore the physics according to their own interests. These experiments either include an incomplete sample code that students must complete, or a complete program in which they can change parameters to observe how the displayed results vary.

It is important to emphasize that the goal of the exercises is to assist and encourage students to work independently through detailed explanations and partially written program codes. Based on the author's personal experience, this approach can lead to a more effective way of learning for most students than assigning a large number of tasks without providing real guidance. A similar conclusion was reached by the author of [3], who introduced active learning elements in a comparable reactor physics course. It is also worth noting that an essential part of the laboratory exercises is providing detailed feedback to students: pointing out mistakes in their solutions and highlighting important observations that may have been missing from their conclusions, and also to reinforce correct conclusions.

In addition to the laboratory exercises, assessment is based on a total of eight mandatory homework assignments. For these tasks, students receive Jupyter Notebooks that contain only the problem description and the necessary variables. The assignments build upon the material covered in the datalab exercises. For example, one task requires students to create a Monte Carlo simulation to determine the critical radius of a U-235 sphere, using the functions developed in earlier datalabs exploring neutron scattering and multiplication. At this stage, students are given greater freedom in how they approach the problem and in the code they choose to implement.

It must be highlighted that although several methods are implemented from first principles by students, still in an introductory course it is not possible to implement tools which allow for studying complicated and heterogeneous problems, while also realistically simulate complicated phenomena (such as thermal scattering). Therefore OpenMC [4] is introduced in the course to allow for the faithful simulation of real world systems (eg. PWR pincells). Due to this choice, the students gain experience in using particle transport simulation software, and become equipped with a powerful tool. The drawback of said choice is, that installing the required software is somewhat difficult. We provide a Docker container to facilitate this, nevertheless the first few weeks of the course involves some troubleshooting each year, to guarantee that all course participants have the necessary software environment to perform the course.

3. PROJECT IDEAS

Since the datalabs and home assignments already allow for assessing student learning, the examination is based on a mandatory project work, which is designed so that students can explore an advanced topic built on their newly gained knowledge within 8–10 work hours. We acknowledge that not all our students will become methods developers, or even part of the nuclear industry workforce; therefore, the projects cover various topics, from nuclear physics to software engineering, with the hope that every student can find something aligned with their interests. The project ideas are titled with possible career paths so that students can appreciate the real-life applications of the skills they have developed over the course. Here, we review the project ideas currently available.

There is an important common pattern in the projects: some means of benchmarking the results are almost always provided, either by pointing to literature where related results are presented or by providing test results. When student–teacher interactions are limited, it has been found that the best way to ensure students do not get off track and end up with incorrect results is to provide them with the correct numerical data.

3.1. The Nuclear Physicist

The goal of this project is to explore the fission barrier. Uppsala University is traditionally strong in research on the nuclear fission process; therefore, many of our physics and PhD students who specialize in the theory of fission are interested in reactor physics primarily as a practical application of nuclear fission. Consequently, we have designed a project assignment for our nuclear physics students based on Reed's simplified fission barrier model [5]. The model considers that as the nucleus begins to split due to some perturbation, the system can be described as two spherical ends connected by a neck. Although the model is an oversimplification of the fission process, where only symmetric fission is considered, it allows for a qualitative demonstration of the fission barrier, and its implementation is an engaging scientific computing task. Reed outlines a numerical integration within a cylindrical mesh superimposed on the nucleus geometry to determine the Coulomb energy of the system. However, we recommend a Monte Carlo–based integration to our students. A solution to the problem, along with some stages of the nuclear fission process, is shown in Figure 1.

3.2. The Nuclear Data Scientist

A limitation of many reactor physics textbooks and lecture notes known to the author is that the nuclear data sources and nuclear data processing are often introduced only with limited detail. Students receive the application libraries for reactor physics software without being given information on how the library is created. In the RFP lecture notes, neutron interactions are also illustrated only in their continuous-energy reconstructed form. Therefore, two projects have been created related to nuclear data, allowing students to explore the details.

One project introduces concepts such as resonance reconstruction, self-shielding, and dilution. This project is similar in structure to the datalabs: students receive extensive descriptions, selected data from

Figure 1. Reed's fission barrier model with the stages of the nucleus deformation.

ENDF files, and code cells to be completed for specific tasks. First, the ENDF format is introduced, and the contents of raw ENDF files are described. Then, the resonance information is extracted from the files, and using the Single-Level Breit–Wigner formalism, the capture and scattering cross sections of U-238 are reconstructed. The resonances are broadened with the Bethe–Placzek approximation. Finally, using Bondarenko's narrow resonance model, self-shielded group cross sections are generated.

Another project explores scattering anisotropy. In introductory reactor physics, when discussing slowing down, isotropic center-of-mass scattering is usually assumed, while pointing out that for low-mass scatterers this results in anisotropy in the LAB system, and that at high neutron energies scattering anisotropy becomes significant. Some textbooks, such as Duderstadt–Hamilton, point out that the average scattering cosine in the CM frame can be given as $\bar{\mu}_c = 0.07A^{2/3}E[MeV]$. However, it is difficult to imagine the distribution based on a single average value, and without visualizing the distribution, students might lack motivation to understand why Legendre polynomials are used to capture scattering anisotropies. In the project, they learn the formats in which angular distributions are recorded in the ENDF files and reconstruct the distribution using the Legendre coefficients. Figure 2 illustrates reconstructed angular distributions for the (n,el) reaction channel of Cu63 (the LANL T2 site presents an NJOY-created plot for the same channel, which can serve as a benchmark). Finally, students explore the impact of anisotropy on the slowing-down decrement, finding that anisotropy in scattering decreases the efficiency of slowing down.

3.3. The Neutronics Analyst

This project prepares students to judge whether the fission source in Monte Carlo calculations has converged. During the course, students perform a large number of Monte Carlo particle transport simulations with OpenMC. The role of inactive and active cycles is mentioned, and the convergence of the eigenvalue is observed. However, the convergence of the fission source is only discussed as a side note. Students selecting this project read the literature on the application of Shannon entropy from Brown [6]. To demonstrate the concept, students construct a simulation with OpenMC. They have freedom to design their own geometry, which can be a loosely coupled array of fuel assemblies in a fuel storage vault,

Figure 2. $Cu63$ (n,el) angular distribution reconstructed from ENDF/B-VIII.0.

as in the example from Brown's paper, or any system in which the fission source converges significantly more slowly than the multiplication factor.

3.4. The Python Programmer

Several students take the course with the goal of deepening their programming skills through practical applications. Therefore, the focus in this project is not on physics but on software. The goal is to create a Python package (with unit tests and documentation) that allows for the estimation of the spontaneous fission rate of a material. Students need to collect and curate a dataset on the half-life and the probability of spontaneous fission. Then they implement a class that describes materials and has methods to estimate the spontaneous fission rate. The students receive a nuclide inventory with the associated spontaneous fission rate evaluated with Serpent2 [7] to test their implementation.

3.5. The Criticality Analyst

The students will explore the 1958 Mayak criticality accident [8] and simulate the neutronic aspects of the accident with OpenMC. In 1958, following a series of criticality experiments, a large tank (75 cm in diameter, 100 cm in height) containing uranyl nitrate solution was emptied. The experimenters first, following safety procedures, began draining the contents of the tank into small, favorable-geometry bottles with a volume of 6 liters each. After several bottles were filled, the experimenters considered the remaining solution in the large tank to be safely subcritical and therefore decided to speed up the process by unbolting the tank from its stand in order to pour the solution directly into the bottles.

The exact container movement is unknown. It seems likely that the experimenters were slowly tilting the container, meaning that with limited sloshing, the liquid would have taken on its steady-state shape. Therefore, as an academic exercise, it is meaningful to investigate the problem by evaluating the multiplication factor of the liquid at various tilting angles. The height of the liquid at a tilted position is not trivial; therefore, students receive a Python module that can evaluate the surface plane. Using this module, they can implement an OpenMC model parameterized by the tilting angle and evaluate the change in the multiplication factor. They observe that tilting the container, and therefore changing the surface-to-volume ratio, can introduce as much as 30,000 pcm reactivity into the system.

3.6. The Experimental Reactor Physicist

The course is evidently focused on simulation and computation. In the best of worlds, any reactor physics course would be accompanied by a practical reactor operation session. Unfortunately, Sweden does not have a training reactor anymore, and within the scope of this distance learning course, the closest we can come to the experience is by using a reactor simulator instead. In this project, the students can choose to use the TRIGA simulator [9] developed by the Jožef Stefan Institute, which, as far as the startup process and operating the reactor are concerned, enables an experience surprisingly close to the actual operation of a reactor.

In the project, students, after setting a realistic control rod worth curve, will start up the reactor while performing a $1/M$ exercise (in lieu of detector counts, the inverse of the power is used) as shown in Figure 3. After they have made the reactor critical at zero power, they investigate control rod oscillation and the temporal change of delayed neutron precursors. Then they begin to increase the power to observe the point of adding heat and the effects of reactivity feedbacks.

By performing several pulse experiments (optionally through automation using scripting), they explore the relationship between the reactivity squared and the peak power as in [9]. Finally, they determine the equilibrium reactivity worth of Xenon in the reactor at a stable 50 kW power. Here, the possibility to speed up time in the simulator is actually advantageous compared to a real experiment. To benchmark their experimental results, students also have to extract the related constants from the source code of the simulator and calculate the expected Xenon worth by applying the relevant formulae.

Figure 3. $1/M$ startup experiment with the JSI TRIGA simulator.

3.7. The Multiphysicist

One shortcoming of introductory reactor physics courses is that they primarily focus on the neutronic aspects of nuclear reactors; therefore, several real-life aspects, such as temperature distributions over the reactor channels, are ignored. In this project, students investigate the axial temperature profile around fuel pins, and the temperature distributions are even used iteratively to find the equilibrium state in the neutronic calculations, as would be done in typical nodal simulators. The students implement a simplified thermal-hydraulics solution and externally couple it to OpenMC by discretizing the coolant material axially. The project is inspired by the minimal coupling script example from the Serpent2

developer team.

In such a simple problem, the benefits of iteration are limited (the infinite multiplication factor of the system converges within two steps). Nevertheless, the exercise demonstrates the basic idea behind iterating the power distribution to equilibrium. Furthermore, students gain first-hand experience of the coolant temperature distribution, which differs significantly from the initial axially independent guess.

3.8. The Reactor Physicist

As stated before, it is not expected that most of the students finishing the course will pursue reactor physics methods development, but we wanted to prepare a project for the few who might. Reactor physicists need various tricks and approximations to solve the neutron transport problem. The main trick is to produce homogenized cross-section data in reflected-boundary assembly-level models and then use that data in nodal diffusion codes. Usually, the difficulty in introducing all the steps involved in reactor calculations is that each step in itself could be a full lecture. Although each step is described with seemingly simple equations, in order to truly interact with these approximations in isolation, students need to be provided with prepared input data; otherwise, appreciating the approximations might be intimidating from the equations alone.

In this project, the critical spectrum correction is explored following the recipes from Stamm'ler [10]. Spatially homogenized cross sections and spectra are created with Serpent2 and provided to the students, who then implement the P1 model. Furthermore, the leakage-corrected results from Serpent2 are also given to the students so they can benchmark their implementation. The expected outcome of the project is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Critical spectrum correction with the P1 method in a PWR pincell.

3.9. Students' Choice

Students are also encouraged to define their own project exercise, and over the years they have submitted work related to the passive safety of small modular reactors, damage calculation of various fuel materials in lead cooled fast reactors, nuclear warhead yield calculations (inspired by the Oppenheimer movie), and machine learning optimization of the Geigner-Nuttal law.

4. FUTURE OUTLOOK

This paper has reviewed the current set of project topics offered in the Reactor Physics with Python course at Uppsala University. The list of available projects is continuously evolving, as we are always looking for new and engaging ideas that can be both rewarding and achievable within a few hours of focused work.

At present, we are developing an exercise to estimate delayed neutron precursor flushing in molten salt reactors, using a Monte Carlo-based approach to sample precursor birth locations and determine the corresponding decay positions. Another task under development focuses on neutron noise analysis using one-dimensional two-group noise methods. We also offer a project on neutron slowing down, exploring Placzek transients and Fermi age; however, this exercise is currently more open-ended in nature, and we have found that it would benefit from some restructuring to make it a more guided learning experience.

Finally, it is worth noting that we plan to develop a similar interactive course focusing specifically on Monte Carlo particle transport methods.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author is grateful to the many colleagues at Uppsala University, especially Henrik Sjöstrand, who have supported the creation and development of this course over the years. The author also thanks E. Branger and C. Gustavsson for reviewing this manuscript.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Course description of Reaktorfyisik med Python" (2025). URL <https://www.uu.se/utbildning/kurs?query=1FA456>.
- [2] "Course material of Reaktorfyisik med Python" (2025). URL <https://github.com/ezsolti/RFP>.
- [3] C. Demazière. "Using active learning in hybrid learning environments" In *Proceedings of International Conference on Physics of Reactors: Transition to a Scalable Nuclear Future, PHYSOR 2020*, (2020).
- [4] P. K. Romano et al. "OpenMC: A state-of-the-art Monte Carlo code for research and development" *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **82**, pp. 90–97 (2015). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030645491400379X>.
- [5] B. C. Reed. *The physics of the Manhattan Project, 4th edition*. Springer, Switzerland (2021).
- [6] F. B. Brown. "On the Use of Shannon Entropy of the Fission Distribution for Assessing Convergence of Monte Carlo Criticality Calculations" In *Proceedings of PHYSOR-2006*, Vancouver, Canada (2006).
- [7] J. Leppänen et al. "Status of Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024" *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.*, **11** (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024031>.
- [8] T. P. McLaughlin et al. "A Review of Criticality Accidents 2000 Revision" *Technical report*, LA-13638 (2000). URL <https://doi.org/10.2172/758324>.
- [9] J. Malec et al. "PC-based JSI research reactor simulator" *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **146** (2020). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2020.107630>.
- [10] R. J. J. Stamm'ler, M. J. Abbate. *Methods of steady-state reactor physics in nuclear design*. Academic Press Inc., London, UK (1983).